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Non-Performing Loans and Profitability of Deposit Money Bank

(Case Study of Commercial Banks Licensed with International Authorization & Commercial Banks Licensed with National Authorization in Nigeria)

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Abstract: *This study examined the relationship between non-performing loans and the profitability of banks, with focus on certain deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive research design. Data relating to the periods 2008-2017 were collated from the Financial Statements of the relevant banks. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation, as computed via the SPSS, was used to test the four hypotheses holding the study. Non-performing loans, as measured by the natural logarithms of Inflation Rate (INF.RATE) and Bank Credit Policy (BCP) represented the independent variable, while Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) represented the dependent variable (Profitability). The study involved a total population of 28 DMBs, from which 10 was drawn into the sample. Further analyses covered measures of central tendencies (mean, median and mode), measures of dispersion (Standard Deviation, Variance, Minimum and Maximum values), ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) and multiple regression models. The results derived showed that whereas BCP has a statistically positive relationship with measures of the dependent, INF.RATE has a statistically negative relationship with the measures of the dependent variable, all at the 95% level of confidence. It is recommended thus, amongst others, that banks regulate lending in accordance with the rise or fall in inflation rate; and if ever loans must be granted, it should be so done with interest elements that favour easy repayment as reflected in the respective banks' credit policies.*

Keywords: *Non-Performing Loans, Inflation Rate, Bank's Credit Policy, Profitability.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The lending system (banks and other financial services providers) involves a number of distinct agents either as primary parties involved (the borrower and the lender) in a relationship, or as auxiliary

entities (auditors, regulators etc). This populated landscape leads to different perspectives and technical jargons when describing the underlying phenomenon namely, a bilateral credit relationship between a borrower and a lender. For this reason still, several perspectives hold sway when trying to report default or what is today referred to as non-performing loans. To appreciate the perspective employed in this study, two of such perspectives must be juxtaposed. From the first, loan is seen to become non-performing when it cannot be recovered within certain stipulated time, subject to some respective laws; the institutional point of view. Secondly, a loan may also be non-performing if it is used in a different way than that for which it had been taken; the borrower's viewpoint. Mohammed et al (2005). In this study however, we will confine our focus to the institutional understanding, in which case, Non-performing loans are loans that have not expired, but it is uncertain whether the borrowers would be often to repay their debts. Kanu Clementia et al (2014). This paper therefore examines the effects on profitability that an eventual default by loan borrowers in Nigeria have with respect to findings from a survey of some Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) [the generic name adopted for all banks- Commercial and Merchant- operating in Nigeria since the commencement of universal banking in 2001].

Logically, Non-performing loans take their name from the fact that they are practically in opposition to the financial situation of the bank. By the time they are referred to as "Non-performing loans", there is the fear that the amounts involved and their interest cannot be fully paid by the debtor. (Chelagat, 2012). In this regard, a financial loss is encountered instead of a profit, leading to adverse effects on the bank. The effects of these non-performing loans are multidimensional; thus they do not only hinder profitability among deposit money banks, but also limit lending to the defaulting businesses, individuals and other corporations.

Research studies have shown that non-performing loans make two major effects on banks. These effects are the limitation of bank's financial performance and lending potential. Following the first effect, increasing bad loans limit the financial growth of banks (Karim, Chan & Hassan, 2010). This consequence is as a result of the fact that non-performing loans deprive banks of the needed liquidity and limit their capability to fund other potentially viable businesses and make credit facilities available to individuals. Karim et al. (2010) argues that there are a lot of other viable businesses that the bank cannot explore as a result of the fact that its funds are caught up in non-performing loans. In the face of these consequences, the bank experiences a shortfall in generated revenues (Ghana Banking Survey, 2013), and this translates into reduced financial performance (Karim et al., 2010; Nawaz et al. 2012; Ghana Banking Survey, 2013).

Another effect non-performing loans have on banks, as identified, is a reduction in the bank's lending potential (Karim et al., 2010). Though this has been acknowledged earlier, it is important to discuss it as a primary independent effect. Banks make a greater part of their revenues and profit from lending activities (Karim et al., 2010). As a result, when banks lose much of their lending capital to non-performing loans, it is likely that a greater part of their revenue is lost. Once revenue is lost in one financial year, the capability of the bank to provide access to credit facilities to other businesses and individuals would practically fall in the following financial years. This means that the bank would fail to lend, or it would reduce its amount allocated to lending in the next financial year.

In view of the above problems, as expressed in cause and effect interactions, this paper aims to critically analyze the relationship non-performing loans have with the profitability of banks in Nigeria, using the generalization technique from a result sample of 10 Commercial banks (Deposit Money Banks-DMBs). More specifically, we shall be trying to show the relationship between the proxies of profitability, as captured by such dimensions as Return-On-Assets (ROA) and Return-On-Equity (ROE), and those of Non-performing loans, as dimensioned by Inflation Rate (INF.RATE) and Bank Credit Policy (BCP) respectively.

In order to achieve our research purpose, the hypotheses below stated in their null forms would be tested:

HO1 Bank Credit Policy does not have any significant relationship with Return-on-Assets of banks in Nigeria.

- HO2 Bank Credit Policy has no significant relationship with Return-on-Equity as a measure of profitability.
- HO3 Inflation Rate has no significant relationship with the Return-on-Assets of banks in Nigeria.
- HO4 Inflation Rate has no significant relationship with the Return-on-Equity of banks in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In surveys of divulging prominence such as this, foundation needs be laid on germane set of ideas in order to guide judgement of results, as we advance into the more salient aspects thereof. Thus, we consider theories underpinning this research subject as well as certain concepts demanding proper treatment.

2.1. Theoretical Framework

In this study, scrutinized and qualified for application is the following set of theories in their under-schemed dimensions:

- Credit Default Theory (As postulated by Wilson Sy in 2007)
- Risk-bearing Theory of Profit (As developed by Prof. Hawley in 1907)
- Credit Market Theory (As advocated by Ewert, 2000)

2.1.1. Credit Default Theory

The Credit Default is a theory relevant for situations where there exists indirect relation to the effect of default that affects the financial performance of a bank. As postulated by Wilson Sy in 2007, this theory is seen to be in corroboration with studies on the relationship between non-performing loans and financial performance; as it recognizes the drivers of Non-performing loans to be ‘Delinquency’ and ‘Insolvency’.

Delinquency is defined as a failure to meet a loan payment by a due date, whereas insolvency is defined as a situation where assets are less than liabilities. The term credit default really revolves around the concept of delinquency. This occurs when a borrower is unable to make a loan repayment by the due date, caused by liquidity failure. Delinquency triggers a solvency assessment which may lead to a conclusion of negative equity position thereby causing loan termination and an expectation of loss by the lender. The theory combines two cardinal variables into a ratio with regard to non-performing loans: “‘Loan’ ‘Serviceability’ Ratio (LSR)” which is defined as the maximum loan interest rate an owner-occupier borrower can service a loan amount from net disposable income after living expenses.

The evolution of this Loan Serviceability ratio (LSR) stems from the fact that serviceability changes over time due to changes in both individual circumstances and the economic environment. A loan which may have started off as being an easily serviceable loan may become a struggle for the borrower due to unanticipated adverse developments, say inflation in the economy, a raise in exchange rates, etc.

2.1.2. Risk-bearing Theory of Profit

The risk bearing theory was developed by the American economist prof. Hawley Frederick Barnard in his book “Enterprise and productive process” published in 1907. According to this theory, profit is a reward for risk bearing. Prof. Hawley justifies his views in the following manner.

Some risk is inherent in every business. This is because all businesses are more or less speculative, thus, profit is not reward for differential ability. The essential function of the entrepreneur is the risk taking because he cannot delegate this function to anybody else; he alone has to bear the risk and profit is the reward for this risk taking.

In the context of this study hence, banks in the financial business of rendering credit services face the risk of default. However, they must not hinge on this in their judgments, but find viable means of curbing this risk to their favour and earning the wages of compliance by borrowers and fine profitability standing.

2.1.3. Credit Market Theory

This model of the neoclassical credit market postulates that the terms of credits clear the market. If collateral and other restrictions (covenants) remain constant, the interest rate is the only price mechanism. With an increasing demand for credit and a given customer supply, the interest rate rises, and vice versa. It is thus believed that the higher the failure risks of the borrower, the higher the interest premium (Ewert et al, 2000).

2.2. Conceptual Framework

Logical understanding of the spectaculars in this study forms the motive for this section. For this cause, a handful of concepts have been considered due-to-be-explained for keener participation and flow of readers; such concepts as the basic Non-performing Loan, Bank profitability and Credit Risk Management-(the Independent, Dependent and Moderating variables respectively.)

Our conceptual framework for this study is summarized in the diagram below:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The pattern of study will be descriptive. According to Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2009), “descriptive survey research design is meant to give an output of statistical information about an aspect of a study that is of interest to policy makers in a bid to aid them in making informed decisions”. The anticipated outcome of this study will thus be a quantitative feed on the relationship between Non-performing loans and the profitability of banks using a handful of Deposit Money banks in Nigeria. The unit of analysis will be at the organizational level. Data collection for study will be purely secondary and shall be used, applying clearly specified statistical measures.

3.2. Population of the Study

The general population of study encloses all Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The entire population for study hence consists of the 28 Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. However, the nature of this study permits only a handful of Deposit Money Banks into focus.

3.3. Sample Size

Since this study is an investigation into Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria, the sampling frame will include all Deposit Money Banks in their licensed categories. From this frame however, 10 Commercial banks will constitute the study as drawn through judgmental sampling technique. They include:

Table 1: Sampled banks for study.

S/No	Commercial Banks Licensed With International Authorization	S/No	Commercial Banks Licensed With National Authorization
1.	United Bank of Africa Plc.	1.	Ecobank Nigeria Plc.
2.	Zenith Bank Plc.	2.	Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc.
3.	Access Bank Plc.	3.	Sterling Bank Plc.
4.	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc.		
5.	First Bank Nigeria Limited		
6.	Fidelity Bank Plc.		
7.	Diamond Bank Plc.		

3.4. Data Collection Method

Secondary data will in the main be used as basis for advancing findings. As such, financial statements in denominations of the Income Statement and Statement of Financial Position would form the tool for data extraction.

3.5. Data Analysis Technique

The data collected will be presented (tables, charts, figures etc.) before analysis commences .Analysis will be descriptive .The methodology to be adopted will be aided by Excel 2010 and IBM SPSS Version 20 software. Descriptive statistics covers measures of central tendencies and dispersion. Bivariate Pearson correlation, multiple regressions and ANOVA will be used to test the significance of the relationship between NPLs and financial performance of commercial banks operating in Nigeria. The study will employ econometric models to test correlation between proxies as operationalized in the previous chapter. The model is represented by the regression formulae below;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_q X_q + \epsilon(x)$$

Where y in the multiple regression is the dependent variable to be correlated. β_0 is the constant/intercept, ϵ or x is the error term, $\beta_1 \rightarrow \beta_q$ are the coefficients of the independent variables while $X_1 \rightarrow X_q$ are the independent variables.

Since there are two (2) independent variables to be correlated to the dependent, we generate two distinct models from the parent model:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF.RATE + \beta_2 BCP + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF.RATE + \beta_2 BCP + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

4. RESEARCH RESULT

4.1. Computation of Dependent and Independent Research Dimensions

Calculations with secondary data constitute the basis for establishing the relationship between Non-performing loans and profitability of banks. Therefore, considering our specific objectives, our raw data is drawn from corporate websites on published financial statements of relevant banks to cover all variables involved in this study. Expressed as percentages to 2 decimal points, our data on measures of the dependent variable for the past ten (10) years are here had as:

Table 2: Secondary Data on Measures of the Dependent Variable.

YEAR	ACCESS BANK	FIDELIT Y BANK	ZENITH BANK	GTB	STERLING BANK	UBA	STANBIC IBTC	FIRST BANK	ECOBANK	DIAMOND BANK
RETURN ON ASSETS										
2008	1.60	2.44	2.77	2.75	2.76	2.63	2.66	3.15	0.78	1.89
2009	2.93	0.33	1.17	2.34	-3.24	0.92	1.89	2.10	0.72	-1.26
2010	1.52	1.17	1.86	3.42	1.61	0.15	2.10	1.38	1.26	1.19
2011	1.11	0.43	1.93	3.34	1.33	-0.23	1.23	-0.75	1.21	-3.07
2012	2.08	2.15	3.93	4.89	1.24	2.63	1.50	3.12	1.44	2.09
2013	1.89	0.75	3.07	4.40	1.11	2.03	2.76	1.51	0.23	1.98
2014	2.24	1.16	2.75	4.00	0.99	1.64	3.22	2.17	-0.02	1.31
2015	2.55	1.27	2.61	4.01	1.57	2.39	2.31	1.05	-0.42	0.45
2016	2.97	0.50	3.52	4.64	0.88	3.94	2.68	0.30	-3.56	0.59
2017	1.32	0.84	1.43	2.63	0.93	1.44	1.88	0.57	0.42	0.55
RETURN ON EQUITY										
2008	9.65	9.56	13.74	15.64	21.57	21.26	12.03	10.79	5.62	10.08
2009	12.02	1.09	5.59	12.65	-30.08	6.87	8.30	9.99	5.23	-7.70
2010	6.06	3.97	9.51	17.80	15.88	1.15	10.07	7.91	10.20	5.58
2011	5.63	2.18	11.23	21.61	16.33	-2.21	8.94	-4.92	14.17	-23.98
2012	13.30	12.19	21.87	30.09	15.44	23.11	11.86	23.19	13.19	20.67
2013	14.17	4.95	18.94	27.87	12.34	22.85	21.54	14.79	2.42	0.76
2014	16.98	7.92	18.69	25.18	9.64	17.09	26.60	19.36	-0.19	0.64
2015	18.00	8.51	17.59	24.48	13.16	19.79	16.76	8.25	-3.95	3.68
2016	22.77	3.52	23.65	28.65	8.54	30.83	20.02	2.62	-41.35	5.34
2017	9.47	5.73	9.79	15.77	9.46	11.01	14.85	4.89	4.61	4.80

The independent measures are tabulated in sequence. Inflation and Bank Credit Policy rates from 2008 to the present are in per centum, having been drawn from economic reports. Literarily confining bank credit policy to a single figure is quite problematic since the concept is in itself a means to an end (i.e. limiting credit default while promoting the bank's interest). However, it has been found helpful the findings that banks have different basic policies toward credit risk. Some banks are inclined to follow relatively conservative lending practice, while others engage in what are properly termed creative banking practices. These policies reflect partly the personalities of officers of the bank and partly the characteristics of the banks deposit liabilities.

Table 3: Percentage Changes in Banks' Deposit Liabilities.

YEAR	Access Bank (%Δ)	Fidelity Bank (%Δ)	Zenith Bank (%Δ)	GTB (%Δ)	Sterling Bank (%Δ)	UBA (%Δ)	Stanbic IBTC (%Δ)	First Bank (%Δ)	Eco Bank PLC (%Δ)	Diamond Bank (%Δ)
2008	68	115	104	23	73	40	36	17	39	91
2009	15	-6	-1	49	-13	-9	72	71	24	10
2010	9	13	12	8	24	-3	10	8	25	-16
2011	19	71	25	35	104	9	58	34	62	44
2012	109	27	17	22	18	20	24	23	17	51
2013	11	30	18	23	22	26	17	17	13	32
2014	9	2	11	14	15	0.4	19	6	23	24
2015	16	-6	0.8	-0.5	-10	-4	-0.3	-3	1	-17
2016	24	3	17	23	0	19	14	4	26	15
2017	-9	-4	-0.3	-1	4	-1	13	-4	32	-2

Thus, a bank with fluctuating deposit liabilities in a static community will tend to be a conservative lender, while a bank whose deposits are growing with little interruption might follow more liberal credit policies. Hagos .M. (2010). It therefore follows syllogistically that bank with conservative lending policies, as reflected in their vacillating levels of deposit liabilities, witness high levels of non-performing loans which account for their discretionary reluctance to lend galore and vice versa. Deposit liabilities are displayed in the liabilities section of a bank's statement of financial position and separated appropriately into deposit from banks and deposit from customers (which we are using). Statistically, percentage change in (customers') deposit liability is given by the formula:

$$\frac{\text{Current yr. deposit balance} - \text{Previous yr. Deposit balance}}{\text{Previous yr. deposit balance}} \times 100$$

Having obtained an averaged variable sum for each and every sampled bank, our independent and dependent research values are made present below:

Table 4: 10-Year Variable Summary for Analysis.

YEAR	Independent Variables		Dependent Variables	
	INF.RATE	BCP	ROA	ROE
2008	11.60	60.60	2.34	12.99
2009	12.50	21.20	0.79	2.40
2010	13.70	9.00	1.57	8.81
2011	10.80	46.10	0.65	4.90
2012	12.20	32.80	2.51	18.49
2013	8.50	20.90	1.97	14.06
2014	8.00	12.34	1.95	14.19
2015	9.00	-2.30	1.78	12.63
2016	15.70	14.50	1.65	10.46
2017	16.50	2.77	1.20	9.04

4.2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Our data analysis shall be consistent with our research questions drawn and hypotheses accordingly. Worthy of note however is that our correlation results, computed via the SPSS, shall mainly be utilized in addressing these research questions and Hypotheses, following which other such models as the regression model and measures of central tendencies, including measures of dispersion would be analyzed to complement results. Hence, we have:

Table 5: Pearson Correlation Table as computed via the SPSS.

		Correlations					
		INF.RATE	BCP	ROA	ROE		
INF.RATE	Pearson Correlation	1	-.125	-.264	-.319		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.731	.461	.369		
	N	10	10	10	10		
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	0	.010	-.011	-.019	
		Std. Error	0	.305	.207	.203	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1	-.833	-.662	-.737
			Upper	1	.499	.135	.078
BCP	Pearson Correlation	-.125	1	.146	.016		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.731		.688	.965		
	N	10	10	10	10		
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	.010	0	.009	.007	
		Std. Error	.305	0	.410	.314	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	-.833	1	-.746	-.641
			Upper	.499	1	.818	.598
ROA	Pearson Correlation	-.264	.146	1	.939**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.461	.688		.000		
	N	10	10	10	10		
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	-.011	.009	0	.000	
		Std. Error	.207	.410	0	.038	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	-.662	-.746	1	.856
			Upper	.135	.818	1	.992
ROE	Pearson Correlation	-.319	.016	.939**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.369	.965	.000			
	N	10	10	10	10		
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	-.019	.007	.000	0	
		Std. Error	.203	.314	.038	0	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	-.737	-.641	.856	1
			Upper	.078	.598	.992	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

c. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 1000 bootstrap samples

4.3. Multiple Regression Analysis

Our Multiple Regression models used for analysis are stated below:

$$\text{Model 1(a): ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INF.RATE} + \beta_2 \text{BCP} + \beta_3 \text{MER} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\text{Model 2(b): ROE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INF.RATE} + \beta_2 \text{BCP} + \beta_3 \text{MER} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Table 6: Multiple Regression Table as Computed via the SPSS.

Model (M) Summaries ^{a,b}									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1.	.287a	.083	-.179	.66483	.083	.315	2	7	.739
2.	.320b	.102	-.154	5.08848	.102	.400	2	7	.685
R ^a ; Predictors: (Constant), BCP, INF.RATE					R ^b ; Predictors: (Constant), BCP, INF.RATE				
M ^a ; Dependent Variable: ROA					M ^b ; Dependent Variable: ROE				

The multiple regression models yielded correlation (R) values of 0.287 and 0.320 respectively upon computation of the strength of relationship in each case between the dependent variable (ROA) and the independent variables (INF.RATE & BCP); and between the dependent variable ROE and the independent variables (INF.RATE & BCP). These depict good linear relationship between predicted and explanatory variables. The model however produced negative determinants owing to R-square (Co-efficient of Determination) values of 0.083 and 0.102 which were adjusted for errors to -0.179 and -0.154. These indicate that the independent variables explain only 8.3% and 10.2% in the main and -17.9% and -15.4% (as adjusted) of the changes in financial performance as measured by ROA and ROE respectively.

Still under our multiple regression analysis, we have our regression coefficient table as:

Table 7: Regression Coefficient Computation via the SPSS.

Coefficients ^{a,b}								
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
1	(Constant)	2.187	.997		2.193	.064		
	INF.RATE	-.053	.077	-.250	-.684	.516	-.235	.129
	BCP	.004	.011	.115	.314	.762	-.023	.030
2	(Constant)	17.158	7.633		2.248	.059	-.890	35.206
	INF.RATE	-.526	.589	-.322	-.893	.402	-1.920	.867
	BCP	-.006	.087	-.024	-.066	.949	-.212	.200
1. Dependent Variable: ROA								
2. Dependent Variable: ROE								

The coefficient table above as given, stems from analyses of our multiple regression models. From model one (1), it is indicated that, based on the model, when other factors (Inflation rate [INF.RATE] and Bank Credit Policy [BCP]) are at zero, the profitability measure (ROA) will be 2.187. However, holding inflation rate constant, a unit increase in banks' credit policy would lead to a 0.004 (0.4%) increase in ROA as a measure of profitability. Again, holding bank credit policy constant, a unit increase in inflation rate would lead to a 0.053 (5.3%) decrease in ROA.

From model two (2), it is indicated that, based on the model, when the independent variables (Inflation rate [INF.RATE] and Bank Credit Policy [BCP]) are at zero, the ROE profitability measure will be 17.158. However, holding inflation rate constant, a unit increase in bank credit policy would necessitate a 0.006 (0.6%) decrease in ROE. Similarly, holding bank credit policy constant, a unit increase in inflation rate would bring about a 0.526 (52.6%) decrease in ROE.

4.4. Measures of Central Tendencies & Dispersion

Next in line, the Measures of central tendencies and dispersion for each variable are presented as:

Table 8: Table of Values for Basic Statistical Measures

Statistics	Statistic	Bootstrap ^b					
		Bias	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval			
				Lower	Upper		
N	Valid	INF.RATE	10	0	0	10	10
		BCP	10	0	0	10	10
		ROA	10	0	0	10	10
		ROE	10	0	0	10	10
	Missing	INF.RATE	0	0	0	0	0
		BCP	0	0	0	0	0
		ROA	0	0	0	0	0
		ROE	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	INF.RATE	11.8500	-.0008	.8561	10.1610	13.5897	
	BCP	21.7910	-.3897	5.8699	10.6294	33.7987	
	ROA	1.6410	-.0033	.1762	1.2492	1.9580	
	ROE	10.7970	-.0158	1.3588	7.7345	13.2084	
Median	INF.RATE	11.9000	-.1656	1.1392	9.0000	13.7000	
	BCP	17.7000	.0931	6.8277	5.8850	33.6500	
	ROA	1.7150	-.0124	.2293	.9950	2.1450	
	ROE	11.5450	-.2947	1.8173	6.8579	14.0600	
Mode	INF.RATE	8.00 ^a					
	BCP	-2.30 ^a					
	ROA	.65 ^a					
	ROE	2.40 ^a					
Std. Deviation	INF.RATE	2.90105	-.18158	.47993	1.68250	3.58752	
	BCP	19.62898	-1.70263	4.26851	8.58061	25.16069	
	ROA	.61216	-.04211	.10841	.33940	.76804	
	ROE	4.73690	-.31432	.93648	2.33959	6.11107	
Variance	INF.RATE	8.416	-.790	2.556	2.831	12.870	
	BCP	385.297	-45.741	147.981	73.628	633.060	
	ROA	.375	-.038	.120	.115	.590	
	ROE	22.438	-2.003	8.125	5.474	37.345	

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 1000 bootstrap samples

Our measures of central tendencies included valuation of the mean distribution, median, mode standard deviation and variance. The result shown in the table is based on the data in the variable table. The table shows the individual characteristics as well as the summary statistics of the data used for the study between 2008 and 2017. Consistent with the table, we conclude that our estimates are statistically significant at the 95% level of confidence.

4.5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Least to be presented is our Analysis of Variance table (ANOVA). ANOVA is a procedure for comparing sample means for one dependent variable (scale data – e.g. statistics exam mark) and for one or more independent variables (categorical data, also known as nominal data – e.g. gender) to see if there is statistically significance difference from which one can infer that the populations from which these samples came themselves are different. Professor Anne .M. (2012).

Table 9: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Table.

ANOVA ^{a,b}					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	.279	2	.139	.315	.739a
Residual	3.094	7	.442		
Total	3.373	9			
2 Regression	20.696	2	10.348	.400	.685b
Residual	181.248	7	25.893		
Total	201.944	9			

a. Predictors: (Constant), BCP, INF.RATE. Computation in respect of ROA.

b. Predictors: (Constant), BCP, INF.RATE. Computation in respect of ROE.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a partitioning of the total variance in a set of data into a number of component parts, so that the relative contributions of identifiable sources of variation to the total variation in measured responses can be determined. From this partition, suitable F-tests can be derived that allow differences between sets of means to be assessed.

Following the ANOVA table, we could conclude that the models were significant owing to F-test values of 0.315 and 0.400, at significance values of 0.739 and 0.685 respectively.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Here, we shall elaborate on our earlier observations, as gotten from our analysis section above. Also, discussions here shall be in accordance with research questions posed and hypotheses proposed, backed up with complementary analyses carried out.

Since our major analyses centered on the correlation table as a basis for establishing the relationships sought, there would be need to properly understand the functioning of the correlation table and its interpretation.

The Pearson correlation gives a summary of the bivariate interactions between the stated variables. Bivariate correlations measure the degree of association between two variables. If the two variables are continuous, the Pearson product moment correlation is an appropriate measure.

The correlation coefficient arrived at from every Pearson computation, ranging from -1 to +1, is both a measure of the strength of the relationship and the direction of the relationship. A correlation coefficient of 1 describes a perfect relationship in which every change of +1 in one variable is associated with a change of +1 in the other. A correlation of -1 describes a perfect relationship in which every change of +1 in one variable is associated with a change of -1 in the other variable. A correlation of 0 describes a

situation in which a change in one variable is not associated with any particular change in the other variable. In other words, knowing the value of one of the variables gives you no information about the value of the other. We shall properly invest meaning to the given literature when discussing our findings.

5.1. Discussion of Findings on Research Questions

1) **What is the relationship between Bank Credit Policy and Return-on-Assets as a measure of bank profitability?**

We discovered in our preceding section that the correlation coefficient estimate of BCP in relation to ROA is 0.146 showing that the variables have a positive relationship, where a one unit rise in BCP brings about a 0.146 (14.6%) rise also in ROA. The result more specifically indicates that an increase in BCP by one unit increases the bank's ROA by 0.146 million naira, on average, per annum. The statistical properties of the result are satisfactory as can be deduced from the R-squared value of 0.083 (8.3%) which shows that the BCP and INF.RATE (as independent variables summarily) explains about 8.3% of the total variations in the profitability of deposit money banks within the period under review. Similarly, as calculated in the regression coefficient, BCP contributes to an upward shift in ROA by 0.4% (holding INF.RATE constant). This is a good indication that banks' credit policy constitutes a veritable tool in the hands of the credit manager for determining the state of the bank's Return on Assets.

2) **What is the relationship between Bank Credit Policy and Return-on-Equity as a measure of bank profitability?**

We discovered in our preceding section that the correlation coefficient estimate of BCP in relation to ROE is 0.016 showing that the variables have a positive relationship, where a one unit rise in BCP brings about a 0.016 (1.6%) rise in ROE. The result further indicates that an increase in BCP by one unit increases the bank's ROE by 0.016 million naira, on average, per annum. However, as computed in the regression coefficient table, BCP impacts negatively on ROE by 0.6% (holding INF.RATE constant). This means that leaving the credit manager with just the bank credit policy as a determinant, the Return on Equity position of the bank stands threatened by a rise in deposit liabilities.

3) **What is the relationship between Inflation Rate and Return-on-Assets as a measure of bank profitability?**

We discovered in our preceding section that the correlation coefficient estimate of INF.RATE in relation to ROA is -0.264 showing that the variables have a negative relationship, where a unit upward shift in Inflation rate reduces ROA by 0.264 (26.4%). The result further indicates that an increase in INF.RATE by one unit decreases banks' ROA by 0.264 million naira, on average, per annum. Also, as calculated and shown in the regression coefficient, INF.RATE in general contributes to a downward shift in ROA by 5.3% (holding BCP constant).

4) **What is the relationship between Inflation Rate and Return-on-Equity as a measure of bank profitability?**

We discovered in our preceding section that the correlation coefficient estimate of INF.RATE in relation to ROE is -0.319 showing that the variables have a negative relationship, where a unit rise in INF.RATE brings about a 0.319 (31.9%) fall in ROE position. The result further indicates that an increase in INF.RATE by one unit decreases the bank's ROE by 0.319 million naira, on average, per annum. Similarly, as computed in the regression coefficient table, INF.RATE impacts negatively on ROE by 52.6% (holding BCP constant).

5.2. Discussion of Findings on Hypotheses Proposed

1) Under our first hypothesis, we found out that Bank Credit Policy has a positive statistically significant relationship with Return-on-Assets of banks in Nigeria. This indicates that on the overall, the level of profitability of a bank relative to its total assets is highly determined by the efficiency of its credit

policy. Where policies are loose, it is only natural to witness a drop in the asset base of the bank and vice versa.

- 2) Under our second hypothesis, we found out that Bank Credit Policy has a positive statistically significant relationship with Return-on-Assets of banks in Nigeria. Same as above, the value of wealth received by Shareholders on amounts invested in banks are highly determined by the stability or else vacillation of deposit liabilities, in other words, credit policy.
- 3) Under our third hypothesis, we found out that Inflation Rate has a negative statistically significant relationship with the Return-on-Assets of banks in Nigeria. This indicates that on the other hand, whereas a bank's credit policy may move hand in hand with its asset contribution margin, rising levels of inflation jeopardizes profit expectations via its negative effect on loan repayment.
- 4) Under our fourth hypothesis, we found out that Inflation Rate has a negative statistically significant relationship with the Return-on-Equity of banks in Nigeria. Consequent upon this discovery, inflation rate is seen to do no good to shareholders. By this, it stands as a major determinant of investment decisions. Banks hence must bring the interests of their shareholders to bear when giving out loans, while considering the level of inflation.

6. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

6.1. Summary

The study is a bracing attempt to ascertain the relationship between Non-performing loans and profitability with reference to the DMBs in the Nigerian banking industry. Findings from miscellaneous other researchers suggest some bank specific factors as well as economic factors including bank lending rate, total asset base of bank, interest rate charged on loans, etc.; Inflation rate, total advances & loans, gross domestic product and the likes to play major roles in determining non-performance of loans in the Nigerian banking industry.

Consequently the study model included Inflation Rate (INF.RATE) and Banks' Credit Policy (BCP) as variables of interest. The result of the study passed several relevant diagnostic tests including reliability tests (for the primary data), Pearson Correlation (for Secondary data), multiple regression, ANOVA, Measures of Central Tendencies and dispersion. At the 95% level of confidence, results show that both proxies of the independent variable have negative relationships with proxies of the dependent variable.

6.2. Conclusion

The conclusion for this study spreads to include the findings that:

Bank Credit Policy has a directly positive significant relationship with the Return-On-Asset position of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria;

Bank Credit Policy has a directly positive significant relationship with the Return-On-Equity position of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria;

Inflation Rate has an inversely negative significant relationship with the Return-On-Asset position of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria; and

Inflation Rate has an inversely negative significant relationship with the Return-On-Equity position of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1. Recommendations based on Research Study

From the study conducted, recommendations are geared to sooth the problems stated and more specifically provide solutions to the adverse relationships diagnosed from findings.

1. On the relationship between Banks' Credit Policy and Return-on-Assets, the following are recommended;

BCP contributes to an upward shift in ROA by 0.4% (holding INF.RATE constant). As such, banks should devote greater attention to their credit policies by:

- Tightening credit policies;
- There should be an increase in collateral requirements;
- According to Uzoamaka .O. (2017), Proper KYC (Know Your Customer) and KYB (Know Your Business) should be done prior to loan processing. This is to assure the bank of the possibility of recovering loans at ease following customer knowledge.
- There should be incorporation of key-man insurance for all loans. (Key-man insurance talks of insurance against death of borrower or disability of the principal requesting loan.

2. On the relationship between Banks' Credit Policy and Return-on-Equity, the following are recommended

- Banks should conduct credit checks and character of the contractor and contractee to ensure shareholders' funds are appropriately invested.

3. On the relationship between Inflation Rate and Return-on-Assets, the following are recommended:

- Interest rates should be reduced to a single digit so as to properly define the interest element to a whole sum, while sparing the borrower the decimal intrusions into cash reserves, especially in periods of economic adversity.
- Upon application for loans, clients should request for disbursement in tranches if possible, to ensure that every penny is spent judiciously and repayments are assured. Uzoamaka .O. (2017).
- Banks should give loans following proper study of the trend in rise or fall in economic inflation rate. This will play a large role in predicting repayment behaviour of clients.

4. On the relationship between Inflation Rate and Return-on-Equity, the following are recommended:

- There should be confirmation of contract papers, invoices and direct payments to clients in order to reduce diversion of funds.

7.2. Recommendations for Further Studies

Some other studies that could be conducted by up-coming researchers in relation to this study, but outside its coverage include:

- 1) The Impact of Bank Verification Number (BVN) on the Incidence of Non-Performing Loans in the Nigerian Banking Sector.
- 2) The Place of World Accounting Bodies in Harmonizing Interest Rate on Loans across Nations.

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